

Methodology and Results from Five Years of Research on 12 Hemp Varieties (2019-2023), Latvia.

Veneranda Stramkale^{1,2}, Laura Andze^{2,3*}, Larisa Cernova^{1,2}, Erika Teirumnieka⁴, Inese Filipova³, Aldis Stramkalis^{1,2}, Edmunds Teirumnieks⁴ and Martins Andzs³

¹ Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics, Department of Plant Breeding and Agroecology, Vilani, Latvia; veneranda.stramkale@arei.lv (V.S.), larisa.cernova@arei.lv (L.C.), aldis.stramkalis@arei.lv (A.S.)

² Agriculture Science Center of Latgale, Vilani, Latvia; laura.andze@kki.lv (L.A.); veneranda.stramkale@arei.lv (V.S.); larisa.cernova@arei.lv (L.C.); aldis.stramkalis@arei.lv (A.S.)

³ Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry, Riga, Latvia; laura.andze@kki.lv; (L.A.) inese.filipova@kki.lv, (I.F.) martins.andzs@kki.lv (M.A.)

⁴ Rezekne Academy of Technologies, Faculty of Engineering Rezekne, Latvia; erika.teirumnieka@rta.lv (E.T.1), edmunds.teirumnieks@rta.lv (E.T.2)

* laura.andze@kki.lv; Tel.: +37122440088.

A field experiment was conducted at the Agriculture Science Center of Latgale in Vilani (56°56'34"10"N, 26°58'01"E, elevation 115 m), Eastern Latvia, from 2019 to 2023. The study was conducted in an area with loam humic gleyic podzol soil typical of the Latvian Eastern region. The main agrochemical parameters of the arable soil layer were characterized with 7.0±0.2% content of organic compounds, 182±13 mg kg⁻¹ P₂O₅, 139±16 mg kg⁻¹ K₂O, pH at 7.2±0.2. The study utilized 12 different hemp varieties, including seed hemp varieties 'Adzelvieši,' 'Pūriņi,' 'KA-2-2011', 'Loja' (Latvia), 'Finola' (Finland), 'Henola' (Poland), 'Estica' (Estonia), and fiber hemp varieties 'USO 31' (Ukraine-France), 'Futura 75', 'Futura 83' (France), 'Bialobrzeskie' (Poland) and 'Austa' (Lithuania). Except for 'Henola,' the hemp seed varieties analyzed in this study are dioecious, meaning that male and female flowers are found on separate plants. In contrast, the seed hemp variety 'Henola' and the fiber hemp varieties investigated are monoecious, with both male and female flowers on the same plant. In dioecious hemp varieties, male flowers began to bloom approximately 40 to 50 days after planting, while female flowers appeared 50 to 60 days following sowing. In contrast, monoecious hemp varieties initiated flowering between 70 and 80 days after sowing. Regardless of the variety, the overall flowering duration lasted between 50 to 60 days. The field trials were arranged in a randomized complete block design with four replicates for each variety for each year. Each plot size was 25m². Hemp varieties were sown at the beginning of May (7.-13.05. depending on the year) using an experimental sowing machine (SN-16) with an inter-row spacing of 12.5cm and a seeding rate of 60 kg per hectare. After the first soil cultivation, 300 kg per hectare of Yara Mila NPK(S) 18-11-13(7) complex fertilizer was applied. Additionally, 35 days after sowing, 60 kg per hectare of nitrogen fertilizer AN 34 N was added to the plots.

Seven weeks after sowing during the vegetation period, every three weeks, hemp plant length was measured on 10 marked plants in each plot as four replicates for each sample. At the beginning of September, 19 weeks after sowing, the hemp plants from one square

meter of each plot were harvested manually using a hand trimmer, and the plant density was tallied by calculating the number of plants per square meter. To determine the biomass yield, the weight of the harvested hemp plants was measured right after harvesting. Then, hemp plants were dried in a hangar using a warm air generator before further processing. Once the green plants were dry, hemp stems were harvested and weighed, and their average length was recorded. The dried samples were manually beaten to extract the seeds, which were then cleaned and weighed using a sample cleaner “MLN” (PFEUFFER, Germany). The seeds’ mass and oil content were measured using an Infratec 1241 Detector Unit (FOSS, Denmark). The hemp stems were processed with a decorticator to separate the fibers and shives, and the fiber content was determined for each sample by weighing the fiber mass.

Mean temperature, °C						
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	1983-2023
April	8.1	5.2	5.4	5.0	8.0	4.3
May	12.3	9.7	10.7	10.0	11.4	11.1
June	18.9	18.7	21.8	17.3	16.5	14.8
July	15.3	16.3	19.3	17.3	16.7	16.9
August	15.8	16.7	13.9	19.5	19.3	15.5
September	11.1	13.6	9.8	9.0	15.6	10.7

Rainfall, mm						
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	1983-2023
April	0	27.1	22.4	40.9	27.2	32
May	69.8	84.7	95.5	70.2	28.1	52
June	48.4	73.1	44.8	108.5	24.9	75
July	92.9	66.3	1.2	44.7	53.2	81
August	105.4	60.0	44	87.6	98.6	71
September	65.3	43.3	35.9	17.3	61.5	62

Plant density, plants/m²							
Varities	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	195	227	197	226	201	209	7
Purini	187	242	236	231	185	216	12
KA-2-2011	223	196	235	241	198	219	9
Finola	230	200	227	229	203	218	7
Henola	198	231	229	211	202	214	7
Estica	212	204	208	205	211	208	2
Loja	218	195	206	216	198	207	5
USO-31	170	217	188	215	178	194	10
Futura 75	182	242	239	204	191	212	12
Futura 83	190	248	224	249	202	223	12
Austa	174	229	218	179	225	205	12
Bialobrzeskie	208	249	255	258	215	237	11

Varieties	Plant length after 7 weeks					Plant length after 10 weeks				
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Adzelviesi	62.7	63.5	64.7	64.6	59.6	84.9	89.2	93.5	86.3	81.3
Purini	68.9	71.2	76.3	69.6	64.8	93.2	114.7	122.6	101.2	88.3
KA-2-2011	57.5	63.2	52	75.6	53.2	92.8	121.3	108.5	127.1	85.4
Finola	64.2	71.8	59.9	81.6	62.5	87.6	90.2	87.5	111.6	67.7
Henola	59.8	71.4	51.9	74.6	70	87.5	103.8	87.2	103.1	96.4
Estica	48.2	69.6	49.3	68.2	66.9	82	105.8	85	102	94.6
Loja	53.2	69.6	59	58	54.5	74	79.7	69	82	64.7
USO-31	59.2	70.6	61.2	78.9	54.7	127.6	139.4	120.2	136	144
Futura 75	69.7	84.9	69.5	81.6	80.7	138.5	139.3	153.2	141.2	163.3
Futura 83	68	85.7	68.7	79.4	82.6	146.3	153.2	143	152	154.1
Austa	50.9	62.1	61	66.6	41.9	119.5	128.6	120	119.6	132.7
Bialobrzeskie	51.9	54.9	52.7	67.2	56.7	91.2	94.2	97.3	100.2	95.7

Varieties	Plant length after 13 weeks					Plant length after 16 weeks				
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Adzelviesi	89.1	94.3	97.7	90.8	90.8	92.4	95.2	98.3	91.5	91.5
Purini	108.2	123.5	130	116.5	100.8	109	124.8	130.5	118.6	101.2
KA-2-2011	110.6	136.2	121.7	144.4	104.2	111	137	121.7	145.8	104.2
Finola	92.4	99.2	92.4	123.5	71.1	92.4	99.5	92.4	124.2	71.1
Henola	95.6	111.7	93.5	110.4	107.6	96.6	112.2	93.5	112.4	107.6
Estica	94.7	114.7	94	112	108.2	95.4	116.2	100	115	102
Loja	77.2	82.3	70	75	69.2	77.2	82.3	70.1	75.1	69.2
USO-31	157.9	163.2	140.9	174.4	178.3	177.2	187	149.4	188.4	208.9
Futura 75	186.8	191.3	171.5	193.8	201.7	214.3	227.2	189.3	239	234.1
Futura 83	172.8	186.4	163	179	197.2	235.1	230.1	245	220	232.5
Austa	154.7	174.3	136.3	176.6	180.3	172.1	192.3	142.3	201.4	203.3
Bialobrzeskie	127.2	126.9	135.6	143.3	133.3	161.9	159.6	154	168	160.4

Biomass, t·ha⁻¹							
Varieties	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	16.3	14.9	11.9	13.7	20.8	15.5	0.7
Purini	19.4	21.0	15.8	19.4	21.2	19.4	0.4
KA-2-2011	22.8	21.6	17.4	21.8	31.7	23.1	1.1
Finola	13.9	13.7	10.8	19.0	15.75	14.6	0.6
Henola	19.7	19.5	16.4	21.2	31.6	21.7	1.2
Estica	24.3	25.6	21	27.5	39.4	27.6	1.4
Loja	19.5	20.1	15.2	18.1	21.7	18.9	0.5
USO-31	23.5	25.0	24.1	27.3	36.1	27.2	1.0
Futura 75	35.6	39.8	28.4	43.8	57.1	40.9	2.1
Futura 83	41	34.1	30.5	50.2	51.3	41.4	1.9
Austa	31.2	26.6	22.6	32.7	45.7	31.8	1.7
Bialobrzeskie	40.7	45.5	37.2	48.3	64.3	47.2	2.1

Stem, t·ha⁻¹							
Varieties	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	10.0	8.0	6.8	7.8	5.1	7.5	0.8
Purini	14.4	12.2	9	9.7	5.3	10.1	1.5
KA-2-2011	17.5	14.0	11.3	14.2	8.3	13.1	1.5
Finola	8.1	6.9	5.9	10.6	3.3	7.0	1.2
Henola	11.1	9.9	7.3	10.0	6.2	8.9	0.9
Estica	12.2	9.5	6.8	10.2	6.6	9.1	1.1
Loja	7.4	6.3	4.1	6.5	3.8	5.6	0.7
USO-31	21.3	21.6	17.1	19.5	16.9	19.3	1.0
Futura 75	30.2	32.9	23.1	36.5	33.1	31.2	2.2
Futura 83	28.2	29.1	24.4	32.6	27.7	28.4	1.3
Austa	27.1	21.9	15.6	22.9	16.5	20.8	2.1
Bialobrzeskie	26.3	22.8	15.2	25.1	19.5	21.8	2.0

Fibres, %							
Varieties	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	26.4	23.72	25.4	22.85	30.2	25.7	1.3
Purini	27.5	26.86	19.9	22.64	33.83	26.1	2.4
KA-2-2011	27.9	29.12	22.1	20.06	29.63	25.8	2.0
Finola	19.7	24.82	28.9	23.68	31.85	25.8	2.1
Henola	20.1	38.73	33.9	28.64	30.63	30.4	3.1
Estica	18.6	30.5	27.6	26.5	35.43	27.7	2.8
Loja	20.2	34.1	35.6	30.4	30.38	30.1	2.7
USO-31	33.8	40.15	26.7	29.98	34.58	33.0	2.3
Futura 75	37.4	37.88	31.4	31.03	34.53	34.4	1.4
Futura 83	36.2	38.6	30.7	33.4	33.1	34.4	1.4
Austa	42.6	35.92	39.9	41.13	30.63	38.0	2.2
Bialobrzeskie	42.7	40.3	36.9	41.7	35.83	39.5	1.3

Fibres, t·ha⁻¹							
Varieties	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	2.64	1.90	1.73	1.78	1.54	1.92	0.19
Purini	3.96	3.28	1.79	2.20	1.79	2.60	0.43
KA-2-2011	4.88	4.08	2.50	2.85	2.46	3.35	0.48
Finola	1.60	1.71	1.71	2.51	1.05	1.71	0.23
Henola	2.23	3.83	2.47	2.86	1.90	2.66	0.33
Estica	2.27	2.90	1.88	2.70	2.34	2.42	0.18
Loja	1.49	2.15	1.46	1.98	1.15	1.65	0.18
USO-31	7.20	8.67	4.57	5.85	5.84	6.43	0.70
Futura 75	11.29	12.46	7.25	11.33	11.43	10.75	0.90
Futura 83	10.21	11.23	7.49	10.89	9.17	9.80	0.68
Austa	11.54	7.87	6.22	9.42	5.05	8.02	1.15
Bialobrzeskie	11.23	9.19	5.61	10.47	6.99	8.70	1.05

Seeds, t·ha⁻¹							
Varieties	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	1.81	2.17	1.78	2.12	1.8	1.94	0.09
Purini	2.12	2.25	2.16	2.2	2.04	2.15	0.04
KA-2-2011	1.96	2.12	1.84	2.61	2.38	2.18	0.14
Finola	2.69	2.68	1.8	2.75	2.05	2.39	0.20
Henola	3.8	2.96	3.26	3.54	3.76	3.46	0.16
Estica	1.38	1.72	1.28	1.96	1.52	1.57	0.12
Loja	1.86	2.05	1.67	2.16	1.98	1.94	0.08
USO-31	1.11	1.36	1.28	1.69	1.28	1.34	0.10
Futura 75	0.27	0.42	0.19	0.90	0.83	0.52	0.15
Futura 83	0.36	0.54	0.2	0.58	0.60	0.46	0.08
Austa	0.54	0.61	0.81	1.15	0.86	0.79	0.11
Bialobrzeskie	0.38	0.48	0.35	0.63	0.50	0.47	0.05

Oil, %						
Varities	Average of Year				Average	SD error
	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	36.1	39.08	39.3	35.2	37.42	0.93
Purini	36.8	39.18	40.18	36.25	38.10	0.94
KA-2-2011	37.5	39.05	40.48	36.3	38.33	0.91
Finola	38.1	38.5	40.08	36.625	38.33	0.71
Henola	38.4	38.85	40.75	37.4	38.85	0.70
Estica	38.9	36.7	39.25	35.325	37.54	0.93
Loja	37.9	35.7	40.0	36.65	37.56	0.93
USO-31	28.3	36.38	36.63	33.075	33.60	1.94
Futura 75	34.1	35.15	39.15	34.925	35.83	1.13
Futura 83	32.5	38.6	31.88	28.2	32.80	2.16
Austa	34.2	37.3	36.6	32.7	35.20	1.07
Bialobrzeskie	34.7	34.1	38.55	34.6	35.49	1.03

Oil, t·ha⁻¹						
Varieties	Average of Year				Average	SD error
	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	0.78337	0.69562	0.83316	0.6336	0.74	0.04
Purini	0.828	0.84629	0.88396	0.7395	0.82	0.03
KA-2-2011	0.795	0.71852	1.05653	0.86394	0.86	0.07
Finola	1.02108	0.693	1.1022	0.75081	0.89	0.10
Henola	1.13664	1.26651	1.44255	1.40624	1.31	0.07
Estica	0.66908	0.46976	0.7693	0.53694	0.61	0.07
Loja	0.77695	0.59619	0.864	0.72567	0.74	0.06
USO-31	0.38488	0.46566	0.61905	0.42336	0.47	0.05
Futura 75	0.14322	0.06679	0.35235	0.28988	0.21	0.07
Futura 83	0.1755	0.0772	0.1849	0.1692	0.15	0.03
Austa	0.20862	0.30213	0.4209	0.28122	0.30	0.04
Bialobrzeskie	0.16656	0.11935	0.24287	0.173	0.18	0.03

1000-seeds mass, g							
Varities	Average of Year					Average	SD error
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Adzelviesi	12.46	11.83	13.09	14.27	13.02	12.9	0.4
Purini	13.82	14.35	12.78	13.97	13.55	13.7	0.3
KA-2-2011	10.55	11.17	10.81	10.97	12.51	11.2	0.3
Finola	12.13	12.56	11.82	12.57	11.39	12.1	0.2
Henola	12.56	11.9	14.25	11.77	13.66	12.8	0.5
Estica	16.52	14.35	16.89	17.23	17.27	16.5	0.5
Loja	11.59	13.56	12.78	13.25	13.13	12.9	0.3
USO-31	8.86	8.60	10.69	13.92	14.39	11.3	1.2
Futura 75	12.71	11.88	7.12	12.27	13.85	11.6	1.2
Futura 83	7.23	9.56	7.23	8.73	9.12	8.4	0.5
Austa	10.98	13.6	11.35	11.66	13.48	12.2	0.6
Bialobrzeskie	14.52	13.85	15.21	14.36	15.38	14.7	0.3